

RECENT RESEARCH RESULTS IN STEREO 3-D PICTORIAL DISPLAYS AT LANGLEY RESEARCH CENTER

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Abstract

The utilization of three-dimensional display information, rather than the conventional two-dimensional display of such information, has become an accepted practice in fields such as meteorology, molecular modeling, medical imaging, and Computer Aided Design (CAD). The application of stereo technology has also been investigated for years within the flight display community. These efforts have been particularly intense for helmet-mounted heads-up display applications, as the display of stereopsis cuing information is readily available with binocular helmet systems. Recent efforts are extending the emphasis to head-down display applications, also. While most of these efforts have been effective in the application of stereopsis to particular tasks, a program addressing stereo 3-D pictorial displays from a comprehensive standpoint has not been evident. NASA Langley Research Center initiated such a program in 1988. The program addresses human factors issues and display technology aspects, as well as flight display applications. This paper presents a survey of the research results from this program.

Introduction

In ordinary displays of "real-world" scenes, depth information is provided by such cues as perspective, relative size, shape, interposition, motion, etc. Current electronic technology can provide high-fidelity pictorial displays under flicker-free conditions that incorporate true depth in the display elements through stereo 3-D technology. The application of three-dimensional display information, rather than the conventional two-dimensional display of such information, has become an accepted practice in fields such as meteorology, molecular modeling, medical imaging, and Computer Aided Design (CAD). The application of stereo technology has also been investigated for years within the flight display community.¹⁻⁷ These efforts have been particularly intense for helmet-mounted heads-up display applications, as the display of stereopsis cuing information is readily available with binocular helmet systems.^{1-4, 6} Additional investigations utilizing electronic shutters or polarized filters, rather than helmet optics, to present separate left- and right-eye views in heads-down applications have also been conducted.^{5, 7-11}

While most of these efforts have been effective in the application of stereopsis to particular tasks, a program addressing stereo 3-D pictorial displays from a comprehensive standpoint has not been evident. NASA Langley Research Center initiated such a program in 1988. The program, illustrated in Figure 1, addresses human factors issues and display technology aspects, as well as flight display applications. The subject paper will present a survey of the research results from this program.

The human factors issues to be covered include an investigation of the implicit assumption that use of heads-down stereoscopic displays in flight applications will not degrade the real-world depth perception of pilots using such displays. Additional topics will include measurement techniques and metrics for determinations of stereo 3-D perceptions.

Figure 1. Research Issues and Products

The display technology aspects revolve around both psychophysical relations and computational techniques. Psychophysical aspects include a discussion of the critical accommodation/convergence relationship, a discussion of where and how accurately subjects perceive depth cues placed within the depth-viewing volume, a presentation of the effective region of stereopsis cuing for a stereoscopic display system, and a discussion of scene-to-viewing-volume mapping and the dramatic increase in depth-viewing volume provided by the application of collimated optics to the stereo display source. The computational aspects to be covered include some new computational techniques that furnish the display designer with increased control for exploiting stereopsis cuing.

The application of stereopsis cuing to advanced flight display concepts has also been researched extensively at NASA Langley. These studies demonstrated increased pilot/vehicle performances through situational awareness enhancements of pictorial displays with stereopsis cuing. Stereopsis cuing has been effective in situational awareness enhancements of pictorial displays, and it is expected to be effective also for the declutter of complex informational displays and in providing more effective alerting functions to the flight crew.

Stereopsis Background

High-fidelity, three-dimensional displays that incorporate "true" depth in the display elements are provided by displaying to each eye a disparate view of the visual scene by means of various display hardware systems, such that the right eye sees only the right-eye scene and the left eye sees only the left-eye scene. These hardware systems include refracting or reflecting stereoscopes, and systems that incorporate electronic or mechanical shutters, or polarized or color filters. Helmet systems depend on a direct presentation of each eye view.

In any case, regardless of the display hardware system, graphics software is necessary to create the left- and right-eye stereo-pair images. The graphics generation computer performs this task, resolving the single-view-point visual database stored within it into the desired stereo pair. Figure 2 illustrates the parallax concept that is employed to produce objects behind the monitor screen via stereo pairs. Figure 3 illustrates the concept as it is employed to produce objects at various depths. The heavy horizontal line represents the screen of the display monitor. To present an object that appears at the depth of the screen, the object is drawn in the same location for both stereo-pair views. For objects to appear behind the screen, the object is displaced to the left for the left-eye view and to the right for the right-eye view (with the displacement reaching a maximum value to place an object at infinity). For objects to appear in front of the screen, a displacement to the right is used for the left-eye view and to the left for the right-eye view.

Figure 2. Parallax Induced Depth Perception

Figure 3. Geometric Principal for Producing Left- and Right-eye Views

Human Factors Issues

Figure 4 summarizes the human factors issues to be addressed within the program, including a completed investigation¹² into a fundamental issue in the application of stereo displays. The assumption that use of stereoscopic displays in flight applications will not degrade the real-world depth perception of pilots using such displays is a safety issue that should be resolved prior to any flight application. Stereoacuity tests are traditionally used to measure the real-world depth perception of a subject. This study (synopsized in Figure 5) used such a test as part of the experimental protocol. Eight transport pilots flew repeated simulated landing approaches using both non-stereo and stereo 3-D head-down "pathway-in-the-sky" displays. At the decision height of each approach, the pilots transitioned to a stereoacuity test using real objects, rather than a two-dimensional target test apparatus.

STUDY	FUNCTION	RESULT
Transition In Transport Approach	Short-Term Exposure To Stereo Displays	No Effect On Real World Acuity
Endurance In Tracking/Monitoring	Long-Term Exposure To Stereo Displays	Future
Depth Probes	Real-World Objects Vs. Stereoptically-Produced Probes	Future
Size/Distance Judgements	Depth Perception Measurements	Future

Figure 4. Human Factors Issues

Figure 5. Stereoacuity Experiment

Statistical analysis of stereoacuity measures (averaged over pilots and replicates), comparing a control condition of no exposure to any electronic flight display with the transition data from non-stereo and stereopsis displays, revealed no significant differences for any of the conditions. Clearly, transitioning from short-term exposure to a head-down stereopsis display has no more effect on real-world depth perception (based on stereoacuity) than transitioning from a non-stereo display. However, depth perception effects based on size and distance judgments, and long-term stereo exposure remain issues to be investigated. Additional topics to be addressed within the program will include measurement techniques and metrics for determinations of stereo 3-D perceptions.

Display Technology Aspects

Figure 6 summarizes the display technology aspects to be investigated within the program. The psychophysical and computational aspects vary with the display technique involved, and the figure indicates the present conception of understanding of each aspect for the various display techniques.

UNDERSTANDING	DISPLAY TECHNIQUE					
	CONVEN. MONITOR	COLLIM. MONITOR	HMD's	CONVEN. PROJECT	COLLIM. PROJECT	VAR. FOCAL SYSTEM
PSYCHOPHYSICAL ASPECTS						
Accommodation/Convergence Relations	✓	Partial	TBD	✓	TBD	TBD
Depth-Viewing Volume	✓	✓	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Visual Scene-To-Volume Mapping	✓	✓	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
COMPUTATIONAL ASPECTS						
Viewpoint Separation	✓	✓	✓	Partial	Partial	TBD
Asymmetric Clipping	✓	✓	✓	Partial	Partial	TBD
Parallax Correction	✓	TBD	TBD	✓	TBD	TBD

Figure 6. Display Technology Aspects

Psychophysical aspects

In binocular or monoscopic displays of perspective, "real-world" scenes, a great deal of depth information is provided by such cues as linear perspective, relative size, shape, object interposition, motion perspective, motion parallax, texture gradients, shading, etc. Stereoscopic displays of such scenes add the cues of lateral retinal disparity and the muscular movement and tension cues associated with vergence. In stereoscopic displays, the introduction of lateral disparity initiates vergence to create a perceived depth (see Figure 2). Stereoscopic displays thus produce both the muscular cues and the disparity/vergence cues associated with depth perception.

Accommodation/convergence relations. Other depth cues that are present in real-world viewing are changes in focus (accommodation) and pupil size (although pupil size remains constant for object distances greater than about 3 feet). In stereoscopic displays, the distance that affects both accommodation and pupil size is the screen distance, which remains constant. Thus, the major depth cue missing in the synthetic generation of stereoscopic displays is the change in accommodation with fixation point depth, and it is indeed a major lack, for accommodation and convergence are highly interactive. For a fixed accommodation distance, there is a limited range of vergence conditions that will result in comfortable, clear, fused, single-vision. This implies that for a given screen distance for a stereoscopic display, there are limits to the amount of lateral disparity that is usable by the display designer, both in-front and behind the display screen. How the depth-viewing volume is effected by this accommodation/convergence relationship was determined empirically in a depth-viewing volume experiment.¹³

Depth-viewing volume. Data was gathered comparing perceived depth via subject judgment (from physical probe placements) against computed depth (from lateral disparity calculations) at several viewer-CRT screen distances. Figure 7 presents the 95-percent confidence intervals for perceived depth from the display screen as a function of computed depth from the screen. A straight line with a slope of unity is also presented on the figure, representing the ideal case of perceived depth coinciding with computed depth. For objects placed in front of the screen, the occurrence of severe object blurring limited the usable volume. Increasing the object depth in front of the screen eventually resulted in double vision. For objects placed behind the screen, the depth perceived was increasingly larger than that presented. That is, the farther the object was placed behind the screen, the larger the error became. The range of computed depth, for which perceived depth is somewhat accurate, increases with increasing screen distance, as can be seen by comparing the curves on Figure 7. Thus, a larger usable viewing

Figure 7. 95% Confidence Intervals for Perceived Depth

volume is available for increasing screen distances, for objects placed both in-front and behind the screen. In addition to indicating the available depth-viewing volume at each screen distance for use by display designers, the data revealed the fact that increasing viewer-screen distances provide increasing amounts of usable depth, but with decreasing fields-of-view. This fact importunes a stereopsis hardware system incorporating larger screen sizes or collimation optics to maintain the field-of-view at a desirable level while providing a much larger stereo depth-viewing volume.

Figure 8. 95% Confidence Intervals for Perceived Depth Error

Figure 8 presents the 95-percent confidence intervals for perceived depth error as a function of computed depth, with both normalized to the screen distance, for each of the three screen distances. Normalization of the data reveals similar slopes and intercepts for the three screen distances examined. Subjects were much more accurate in their perceived depth estimates for the in-front images compared to the behind-screen conditions, but, as indicated above, when objects are placed further and further in front of the screen, and closer and closer to the subject, they begin to quickly blur. So even though the distance judgments are more accurate, the usable volume in front of the screen is smaller than the usable volume behind the screen. If one accepts the criteria of comfortable, unblurred single vision in front of the screen, and less than 10-percent perceived depth error behind the screen, the usable depth

viewing-volume falls between -25-percent and +60-percent of the screen distance (the 10-percent error criteria are marked with lines in Figure 8). Thus, the normalization of the data from the individual screen distances provides limits $(-0.25^{\circ}D$ and $+0.6^{\circ}D$) for the depth-viewing volume for a generalized screen distance, D . Table 1 presents these limits for the screen distances examined, along with the corresponding fields-of-view (FOV) for a 14-inch monitor. These limits are suggested as guidelines for practical, usable depth-viewing volumes for stereopsis displays.

Screen distance	Depth of viewing volume	Field-of-view (degrees)
19 inches	16.2 inches	40.0
38 inches	32.3 inches	20.6
57 inches	48.4 inches	13.8
Infinity (collimation)	Very large depth postulated	40.0

Table 1. Stereo Display Viewing Volume

Visual scene-to-volume mapping. Since stereo 3-D viewing volumes have a practical limit to the amount of depth that is viewable and usable, any stereo 3-D presentation maps the "real world" depth to a stereo 3-D virtual image depth. Figure 9 is an illustration of this concept and also depicts the constraints imposed by the limited depth-viewing volumes of directly-viewed time-multiplexed stereo 3-D display hardware, in which the real-world depth cues of hundreds of feet are mapped into a virtual volume with only several feet of depth.

Figure 9. Scene-To-Screen Mapping Using Conventional Stereo Technology

Conventional asymptotic transformations (See Figure 10) allow the display designer to fix a specific scene distance at the screen location in the viewing volume. The remaining scene distances are mapped to the stereo viewing volume according to the asymptotic mapping function selected. The viewer distance to the screen, the "real-world" scene distance desired to appear at screen depth, the interpupillary (interocular) distance of the viewer, and the "real-world" database (scene) distances are

Figure 10. Conventional Asymptotic Visual Scene Mapping

parameters that shape the mapping function. The shape of the mapping function determines how objects in the "real-world" database are distributed throughout the viewing volume (in front of and behind the display screen). The asymptotic nature of the mapping function, as well as its overall shape, is also determined by user-selected limits of the depth-viewing volume: distance from the viewer to the farthest stereo virtual image (maximum viewing distance), and the distance from the viewer to the closest stereo virtual image (minimum viewing distance). The maximum viewing distance establishes the maximum separation of the image in left-right stereo image pairs.

Collimation effects. It is well known from psychophysical research that the effective range of human stereo vision is several hundred feet. However, directly-viewed time-multiplexed stereo 3-D display techniques bestow a virtual volume with only several feet of depth. Recent experiments, as mentioned in the previous section of this paper, determined that the effective region of stereopsis cuing, the depth-viewing volume, increased with increasing viewer-to-screen distances. However, this increase was accompanied by a decrease in the FOV of the system (See Table 1). It was theorized that collimation of the display source would move the effective accommodation distance to near-infinity while maintaining the FOV at required levels, and a dramatic increase in the depth-viewing volume was postulated. This theory was validated in a proof-of-concept test¹⁴. Figure 11 shows photographs of a conventional stereo display in use, and the beam-splitter, reflective mirror collimation system that was borrowed from the Langley Central Simulation Facility for this proof-of-concept investigation. Although the conventional stereo 3-D monitor had a size and a curvature profile that was not matched to the collimation system for accurate use, it was mounted on the collimation system, and subjective determinations of the viewing-volume were made which revealed a one hundred-fold increase in depth compared to the conventional system.

Figure 11. Stereo Display System Hardware

This dramatic increase in depth-viewing volume is a breakthrough in head-down stereo display technology, and will contribute to the full exploitation of stereopsis cuing in advanced display concepts.

Computational aspects

The computational aspects to be covered include some new computational techniques¹⁵ that furnish the display designer with increased control for exploiting stereopsis cuing.

Viewpoint separation. Graphic software within the graphics generator is used to generate the lateral disparities for the stereo pairs. First, left-eye and right-eye coordinate systems are created as offsets from the viewer coordinate system of the visual scene. Clipping is then employed to limit each eye-view to the display surface boundaries. And finally, simple perspective division is used to transform the three-dimensional viewing volumes to two-dimensional viewports, whose centers are offset from the center of the display screen by half of the maximum-allowed lateral disparity (used to represent objects located at, or near, infinity). Conventional computational techniques that are utilized in stereopsis display generation rely on symmetric clipping algorithms and asymptotic transformations to provide the left-eye and right-eye stereo pair. Symmetric clipping algorithms are used to limit the computed view to the display screen boundaries. Asymptotic transformations are used to map the visual scene into the stereo viewing volume.

Asymmetric clipping. Figure 12 presents an illustration of symmetric and asymmetric clipping as well as the effects of using each algorithm. With symmetric clipping, the left side of the left-eye viewing volume is determined by the left edge of the display surface. The right side of the left-eye viewing volume is determined by reflecting the left side about the sight vector, thus producing symmetric angles. In stereo 3-D displays, the left- and right-eye projections are offset from the center line producing unused blank spots on the display surface if symmetric clipping is employed. With a 40° horizontal FOV these blank spots generate two 70 monocular regions on each edge of the monitor with an overlap stereo 3-D region of 26°. This is not the most efficient use of the available resources. Asymmetric clipping, as developed at LaRC, uses the entire display surface for each eye view. The left side of the left-eye viewing volume is determined by the left edge of the display surface, just as in symmetric clipping. The right side of the viewing volume, however, is determined by the right edge of the display surface. This generates unequal, or asymmetric, angles about the sight vector. With asymmetric clipping, there are no unused portions on the display surface with the stereo 3-D overlap region encompassing the entire 40° of the FOV.

Figure 12. Stereo 3-D Clipping Algorithms

The horizontal FOV under discussion is that of the display surface. However, for stereoscopic displays, the perceived FOV varies with the point of fixation within the viewing volume. For objects in front of the screen, the perceived FOV is larger than that at screen distance, while the perceived FOV at infinity is smaller. Asymmetric clipping provides increased FOV (for both stereo regions and the total scene) throughout the depth-viewing volume (see the table portion of Figure 12).

Mapping transformations. Since stereo 3-D viewing volumes have a practical limit to the amount of depth that is viewable and usable, any stereo 3-D presentation maps the "real world" depth to a stereo 3-D virtual image depth (see Figure 9). Conventional asymptotic transformations allow the display designer to fix a specific scene distance at the screen location in the viewing volume. Additional control within the transformation allows some shaping of the asymptotic curve. Although the monocular depth cues (perspective, inter-object position, etc.) usually remain accurate, the intelligent use of the limited, practical depth-viewing volume resource (for traditional stereo 3-D display systems, the depth-viewing volume is on the order of a few feet) is a must if the display is to be used to its full potential. The asymptotic mapping curve has a limited capability to be tuned to a particular task, but the new piece-wise linear approach, as developed at LaRC, allows the depth-viewing volume to be creatively partitioned with depth cues placed at various scene distances where emphasis is desired. Figure 13 shows a comparison of a conventional asymptotic mapping to a piece-wise linear mapping where stereo 3-D depth was placed at two separate regions in the viewing volume.

Figure 13. Visual Scene Mapping to Stereo 3-D Viewing Volumes

Parallax correction. In stereo pictorial displays, the display designer must map the depths in the "real-world" to the depths available with the stereo display system. However, as indicated above, the human subject does not perceive the information at exactly the depth at which it is mathematically placed. Head movements can also seriously distort the depth information embedded in stereo 3-D displays, as the transformations used in mapping the visual scene to the depth-viewing volume depend intrinsically on the viewer location. The top portion of Figure 14 again illustrates the parallax concept that is employed to produce objects behind the monitor screen via stereo pairs. If the subject viewing a stereo display moves away from the display screen, and the lateral disparity remains constant (i.e., is not corrected for this movement), the perceived object will appear to retreat further from the screen (illustrated in the bottom portion of Figure 14). Conversely, if the subject moves forward toward the screen, the object appears to also move toward the screen. Thus any head movement effect is exaggerated by the accompanying object movement. To further confuse the viewer, objects presented in front of the screen perversely move in directions opposite to those of objects located behind the screen (see Figure 15). Therefore, head movements can seriously distort the depth information embedded in stereo 3-D displays.

Figure 14. Head Movement Effects with Constant Lateral Disparity

Figure 15. Object Translations with Head Movement

Two correction techniques are available¹⁶, one to correct the original visual scene to depth-viewing-volume mapping based on known human perception errors, and the second to correct for errors induced by head movements based on head-positioning sensor input data. The first technique of recomputing the depth placement of objects so that they are perceived at the desired depth is a simple linear relation, and data is presented comparing perceived depth error with and without the correction technique in Figure 16. The head-movement correction technique involves transformations to correct the lateral disparity calculations based on head-positioning sensor input data to eliminate these exaggerated and confusing object movements (see block diagram in Figure 17). The algorithm corrects for head movements in all six degrees-of-freedom. However, as fore/aft movement effects are more exaggerated than the other degrees-of-freedom, the results of the verification experiment are reported here for only that axis of movement. Figure 18 presents empirical data from three subjects (nine trials per data point) that validates the movement correction algorithm. The percent of perceived error is plotted against the object depth placement position (both axes are normalized to screen distance) for both a 20-percent backward and a 20-percent forward head movement. Positive error represents objects that are perceived as too far from the viewer, and positive depth placement represents objects placed behind the viewing screen. Data is presented comparing the cases of no head movement, head movement without correction, and head movement with correction, for both forward and backward head movements. A combination of both correction techniques effectively eliminates the distortions of depth information embedded in stereo 3-D displays.

Figure 16. Correction for Perceived Depth Error

Figure 17. Technique for Head-Movement Correction in Stereo 3-D Flight Displays

Figure 18. Parallax Effect With & Without Correction (Normalized to Screen Distance)

STEREO 3-D PICTORIAL DISPLAY APPLICATIONS

The application of stereopsis (true depth) cuing to advanced flight display concepts has also been researched extensively at NASA Langley. Figure 19 synthesizes these studies, which demonstrated increased pilot/vehicle performances through situational awareness enhancements of pictorial displays through stereopsis cuing. Stereopsis cuing has been effective in situational awareness enhancements of pictorial displays, and it is expected to be effective also for the declutter of complex informational displays and in providing more effective alerting functions to the flight crew.

Recovery from flight-path offset

The first application study in stereo 3-D pictorial displays conducted at Langley Research Center dealt with pilot reaction times to an instantaneous displacement from a nominal flight path¹⁷. Two pathway-in-the-sky formats were examined, in both non-stereo and stereo presentations (see Figure 20). The data, presented in Figure 21, show that pilots responded faster with the stereo displays, indicating improved situational awareness. The responses with the signpost pathway were faster than those with the monorail pathway, and the interaction between pathways and stereopsis was also significant, indicating that stereo was more effective in enhancing situational awareness in the case of the poorer information source (i.e., the monorail pathway).

STUDY	FUNCTION	RESULT
Helicopter Hover	• Situational Awareness	• Improved Hover Perf. W/ Velocity Element & Stereo
Emulated HMD Tracking/Monitoring	• Situational Awareness • Alerting	• 33% Improvement In Tracking Perf. W/Stereo • Color Effective, Stereo Not In Peripheral Monitoring
Transport Curved Approach	• Situational Awareness	• Precise Flightpath Control Using "Pathway-In-The-Sky" • 18% Improvement In Range Tracking Perf. W/Stereo
Collimated Transport Approach	• Situational Awareness	• Collimated/Noncollimated; 23% Improv. In Tracking Perf.
Monitoring Declutter	• Declutter	Future
Velocity Streaming	• Situational Awareness	Future
Parallax	• Situational Awareness	Future

Figure 19. Stereo 3-D Pictorial Displays Applications

Figure 20. Study of Recovery from Flight-Path Offset

Figure 21. Reaction Time Results for Flight-Path Offset

Helicopter hover

The first real-time piloted simulation experiment in stereoscopic applications at Langley assessed the efficacy of stereopsis cuing in pictorial display enhancements in a precision rotorcraft "hover in turbulence" task⁹. Seven pilots endeavored to maintain a hover by visually aligning the inner and outer wickets of Figure 22, thus attaining the desired hover position, in a full-factorial experimental design. The visual conditions examined included the presence or absence of a velocity display element (a longitudinal/lateral velocity display indicator), as well as the stereopsis cuing conditions, which included non-stereo (no depth cues), stereo 3-D, and "hyper" stereo. The latter condition represented the case of the pilot's eyes (image sources) being located 6 feet apart (as might be encountered with FLIR cameras mounted on each side of a cockpit for a binocular display), rather than the usual 2 inches, and the condition exaggerated the depth cues present in the display. Objective and subjective results overwhelmingly indicated that the depth cues provided by the stereo displays enhanced the situational awareness and performance of the pilot. The enhancement was particularly effective when the velocity information element was absent from the display (see Figure 23), implying that velocity information, as well as positional information, can be readily extracted from the depth presentation.

Figure 22. Rotorcraft Precision Hover Task

Figure 23. Average RMS Radial Error With Velocity Element On/Off

Emulated Helmet-Mounted Display (HMD)

To provide stereopsis, binocular HMD systems must trade some of the total FOV available from their two monocular fields to obtain a partial overlap region. The visual field then provides a mixture of cues, with monocular regions on both peripheries, and, in the overlapped center, a binoptic (the same image to both eyes) or, if lateral disparity is introduced to produce two images, a stereo region. The goal of this research¹⁸ was to assess the trade-offs arising from the mixture of color cueing and monocular, binocular, and stereopsis cueing information in peripheral monitoring displays as encountered in HMD systems. The accompanying effect of stereopsis cueing in the foveal display of tracking information was also assessed. Since current HMD systems cannot provide the interchangeable capabilities of non- stereo and stereo cueing with color capability, a head-up color CRT stereo monitor configuration was used to present the visual display (see Figure 24). A single-axis vertical tracking task for a rotorcraft, utilizing a "pathway-in-the-sky" format, was chosen as the primary task for the pilot-in-the-loop experiment. A monitoring task (detection and acknowledgment of boundary excursions) was presented in the periphery of the display (see Figure 25). The total 40° FOV was partitioned into a 20° foveal area and 10° left- and right-peripheral areas. The primary tracking task was presented as either a non-stereo or stereo pathway in the foveal area, while the monitoring task was presented in one of the peripheral areas, with the presence (a blue bar turned red whenever it exceeded the excursion boundary) or absence (no color change) of color cueing. Figure 26 presents the primary task performance effects as both possible interpretations of the interaction between color cueing and path display condition for the path error RMS measure. The addition of color cueing to the monitoring task resulted in improvements in the primary tracking task, but only when using a non-stereo pathway (with a 22-percent improvement for the non- stereo and only a 3-percent improvement for the stereo pathways). The addition of stereopsis cueing to the pathway display resulted in improvements in the primary tracking task, with or without color in the monitoring task display (with a 33-percent improvement for the color absent and a 17-percent improvement for the color present conditions). Figure 27 presents the monitoring task performance effects that were significant. The addition of color cueing in the monitoring task display resulted in a 36- percent increase in the number of correct boundary excursions detected by the pilots, and a decrease of 82-percent in the number of extraneous (false) detections.

Figure 24. Binocular HMD Emulation

Figure 25. Display Format and Associated Tasks

Figure 26. Tracking Task Performance Effects

Figure 27. Monitoring Task Performance Effects

The results of this experiment indicate that binoptic display of monitoring information in the right-peripheral region, with color cuing as an alerting function to such information, and stereopsis cuing in the central region of the display, were the most effective display conditions examined. To obtain the advantages of binocular summation with binoptic displays in the peripheral region, a sacrifice in total FOV is required. The performance gains realized from binoptic or stereopsis cuing over monocular display in the periphery requires a loss of total FOV that may not be justified for all applications. To obtain color cuing in HMD systems, significant technology development efforts are required. In order to realize the advantages of stereopsis cuing in the foveal area, an additional image generation source is required for advanced HMD systems.

Transport curved approach

The application of "Real-world", three-dimensional, pictorial displays in the form of "pathway-in-the-sky" formats has been successful in providing complex-path guidance information to pilots of advanced fighter aircraft. Indeed, improved performance with such formats, as compared to conventional formats, has been demonstrated by the Naval Air Development Center (NADC). With the conversion from the present instrument landing system (ILS) to the microwave landing system (MLS) within the National Airspace System, complex-path approaches could be used for commercial transport operations to address airport capacity issues. Therefore, the application of "pathway-in-the-sky" formats to commercial transport operations is being evaluated at various flight display research laboratories, including NASA Langley. The introduction of true depth cues via stereopsis techniques offers a means of further enhancing these displays. The objective of this research was to determine the effectiveness of two competing pathway formats for landing approach, and to investigate the effect of their presentation in Stereo vs. Non-stereo.

The experiment¹⁹ utilized an NADC-like tile pathway and a goalpost pathway as the main factors studied. Figure 28 illustrates the visual task chosen for the comparison experiment (i.e., maintaining range separation with a lead aircraft while flying the desired curved, decelerating, descending, landing approach pattern in turbulence). Separation was regulated with the location of the desired range marker element (a "waterline" symbol). This range marker also provides a non-stereo range cue in that when the lead aircraft is at the desired range, the wingspan of the aircraft is the same width as the ownship symbol (the desired range marker).

Figure 28. Pilots' Visual Range-Tracking Task and Alternate Pathway Formats

Figure 29 presents the mean standard deviation of path error results from 7 Air Force transport pilots who each flew 20 approaches with each display format. The variation in vertical path error, as indicated by the standard deviation, was 10-percent less for the tile format, the variation in lateral path error was 11-percent less for the goalpost format, and the difference in variation in range path error was not statistically significant. Figure 30 compares the mean range error standard deviation for the stereo condition vs. the non-stereo control condition. The inclusion of stereo depth cues improved performance by 18-percent over the non-stereo control condition.

Figure 29. Pathway Format Effects

Figure 30. Effect of Stereo 3-D Presentation on Simulated Landing Approaches

A similar study also assessed the effects of stereopsis cuing upon heart-rate measures, since these measures have been demonstrated to be indicative of pilot stress. Figure 31 shows the mean heart-rate increase, as well as the standard deviation of heart-rate increase, for individual pilots using stereo and non-stereo versions of the pictorial display. The results indicate that stereopsis cues can reduce the amount of stress imposed upon pilots during such a task.

Figure 31. Comparison of Pilot's Heart-Rate Responses to a Non-Stereo/Stereo Landing-Approach Display

Collimated transport approach

Collimation optics can be used to increase the viewer-virtual screen distance to near-infinity, at the same time providing a dramatic one hundredfold increase in depth-viewing volume for stereo 3-D displays. The goal of this research effort was to determine the effectiveness of this increased viewing volume for presentation of advanced flight display concepts. Figure 32 presents the mean range error standard deviation results of the previous experiment compared to the collimated results. In the previous experiment, 7 Air Force transport pilots each flew 24 approaches for each condition (the non-stereo and the conventional stereo conditions). For the collimated display comparison, 7 pilots (including 5 from the original group) flew an additional 24 approaches. The inclusion of conventional stereo depth cues improved performance by 18-percent over the non-stereo condition. The performance with the increased stereo viewing volume improved by 23-percent over the conventional stereo performance²⁰.

Figure 32. Collimation Effects Compared to Previous Study

Future experiments

Future experiments are planned to assess the effectiveness of stereopsis cuing for the declutter of complex informational displays and in providing more effective alerting functions to the flight crew, as well as additional efforts to further enhance situational awareness in pictorial displays.

Concluding Remarks

The NASA Langley Research Center program addressing stereo 3-D pictorial displays from a comprehensive standpoint has yielded numerous important results. The program deals with human factors issues and display technology aspects, as well as flight display applications. The human factors findings include addressing a fundamental issue challenging the application of stereoscopic displays in head-down flight applications, with the determination that stereoacuity is unaffected by the short-term use of stereo 3-D displays. While stereoacuity has been a traditional measurement of depth perception abilities, it is a measure of relative depth, rather than actual depth (absolute depth). Therefore, depth perception effects based on size and distance judgments, and long-term stereo exposure remain issues to be investigated. Additional topics to be addressed within the program will include measurement techniques and metrics for determinations of stereo 3-D perceptions.

Optimal use of stereopsis cuing requires an understanding of the depth-viewing volume available to the display designer. A knowledge of where and how accurately a subject perceives the depth cues placed within the depth-viewing volume is essential to enable effective displays for precision control tasks. The empirical determination of the effective region of stereopsis cuing for a time-multiplexed, directly-viewed stereopsis display system provide the display designer with guidelines to allow more effective placement of depth information in stereo displays. The computational techniques furnish the display designer with increased depth control and stereo FOV for stereopsis cuing, and with more effective cuing. The dramatic increase in depth-viewing volume provided by collimation is a breakthrough in head-down stereo display technology, and will contribute to the full exploitation of stereopsis cuing in advanced display concepts.

The applications of stereo 3-D to pictorial flight displays within the program have repeatedly demonstrated increases in pilot situational awareness and task performance improvements. Moreover, these improvements have been obtained within the constraints of the limited viewing volume available with conventional stereo displays. Future applications, utilizing the increased volume (provided by collimation), which is more commensurate with that of natural vision, have the demonstrated potential of even greater effectiveness.

With the firm foundation provided by the other components of this program, applications of stereopsis cuing as a means of displaying three-dimensional information in a natural way to enhance situational awareness in complex situations offers great promise. Innovative concepts will continue to be sought and evaluated to fulfill that promise, as well as to exploit stereo cuing for effecting the declutter of complex informational displays and in providing more effective alerting functions to the flight crew.

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